

Oxygen vacancy-dependent chemical intermediates on Ru/MnO catalysts dictate the selectivity of CO₂ reduction

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Abstract: The study of the structural dependence of the formation and transformation of the surface intermediates is the key to controlling the catalytic selectivity. The CO₂ hydrogenation may occur via CO or formate intermediates etc., depending on the catalytic properties. However, the multiple sites of heterogeneous catalysts make it very difficult to analyze the synergistic mechanism between each site. Especially a highly controversial issue is whether formate species are spectator or active intermediates. In this work, two Ru/MnO catalysts with different oxygen vacancy densities were designed to clarify this issue. The high-defective RuMn-O_v showed high CH₄ selectivity (i.e. 89.3% for CH₄ at 320 °C), while the low-defective RuMn-C mainly produced CO (i.e. 100% for CO at 320 °C). The characterisation of these samples with multiple techniques, in combination with theoretical modelling, showed that the decisive factors controlling the selectivity and surface pathways cannot be associated with the properties of Ru metal and its reactivity in hydrogenate CO but rather with the formation and transformation of formate species. The formate form on MnO-O_v support and are further hydrogenated to CH₄ by spillover hydrogen surface diffusing from the Ru nanoparticles. In the absence of surface oxygen vacancies, this mechanism is inhibited.

Introduction

Selective hydrogenation of CO₂ is an important research topic that combines meeting carbon reduction targets, carbon circularity in the chemical industry and valorisation of the hydrogen economy by enabling efficient methods for chemical energy storage. The greenhouse gas CO₂ can be the storage carrier for H₂ produced with renewable energy sources, converting it into easily storable and transportable fuels or chemical raw materials such as methanol and syngas^[1]. The primary products of CO₂ hydrogenation at atmospheric pressure are CH₄ and CO, with the former widely used as a fuel and basic chemical and the latter being the fundamental raw material in Fischer-Tropsch synthesis, methanol synthesis, and other fields. Achieving high selectivity for the target product can significantly reduce the separation costs^[2], making it essential to unravel the relationship between catalytic structure and selectivity.

Heterogeneous catalysts exhibit multiple sites, with particular emphasis often placed on the metal or metal-carrier interface as the pivotal factor governing reaction performance, which determined selective formation and transformation of intermediates (such as CO and formate etc.)^[3]. Typically, weakening the CO adsorption strength of metal in favour of promoting its rapid desorption can avoid the complete hydrogenation to methane. This tuning of the performances depends mainly on the electronic configuration and coordination geometry of the active metal^[4]. Various strategies, including i) reducing *d*-electron density^[5], ii) decreasing the particle size^[6], iii) varying the surface properties by strong metal-support interaction (SMSI) effect^[7] and iv) making alloys^[8], have been used to weaken the CO adsorption and enhance the CO selectivity. Even with these advances in designing the catalysts to control the selectivity in CO₂ methanation, the mechanistic question of the key surface intermediates triggering the reactivity from CO to CH₄ remains a matter of debate.

The formate intermediate is often detected, but the structural factors governing its formation and its effective role as a crucial intermediate governing the catalytic selectivity continue to be subjects of debate and controversy^[5, 9]. Wang et al.^[10] reported that Ru/CeO₂ and Ru/Al₂O₃ went through different reaction pathway for CO₂ methanation. Ru/CeO₂ catalyst with formate intermediate exhibited higher methanation activity compared with Ru/Al₂O₃ with CO intermediate. However, other literature results are in contrast with this indication. Bobadilla et al.^[11] compared CO₂ hydrogenation intermediates on Au/TiO₂ and Au/Al₂O₃ catalysts, exhibiting both 100% CO selectivity. The formate forms predominantly formed on the non-reducible support Al₂O₃, while on Au/TiO₂, the reaction goes

through a redox mechanism with the formation of hydroxycarbonyl intermediates. The preceding studies reveal a conspicuous discrepancy between the preferential generation of formate and the reducibility of the support. Meanwhile, it does not present the intermediate dependence of selectivity. In addition, Rabee et al.^[12] confirmed the above indications and suggested that the interfacial Au–O_v–Ti³⁺ sites are responsible for the superior activity of Au/TiO₂. Feng et al.^[13] combined operando diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS) results with density functional theory (DFT) calculations, indicating that the Zn–O–Zr asymmetry site is pivotal in formate formation and transformation to produce methanol. Dostagir et al.^[14] reported that formate intermediates bridging Co and Zr sites form in CO₂ hydrogenation to CO on Co-doped ZrO₂ (isolated Co ions). On the contrary, formate species at the interface between the Co nanoparticles and ZrO₂ support form when Co-nanoparticles are present, and this formate species converts to methane.

The intricate relationship between the structural characteristics and the resulting formate formation, along with its contradictory implications for reaction selectivity, highlights a notable level of complexity. A source of uncertainty is that catalysts with different supports and types of surface metal nanoparticles are compared for different reactions in CO₂ hydrogenation (reverse water gas shift, methanol or methane production). Therefore, there exists a need for a more precise understanding of the synergistic effect of various sites in heterogeneous catalysts regulates the selective generation and conversion of intermediates by limiting the variability to a single factor.

Manganese oxide is a multivalent oxide with a highly adjustable surface structure, making it an excellent support for investigating the dependence of catalytic reactions on surface microstructure^[15]. In this study, we synthesised two RuMn catalysts with distinct densities of oxygen vacancies in the MnO_x supports. They have comparable Ru nanoparticle and MnO_x crystal characteristics. High-defective RuMn–O_v (Ru/MnO_x–O_v) exhibits high CH₄ selectivity, whereas low-defective RuMn–C (Ru/MnO_x–C) has high CO selectivity. Thus, they are excellent candidates for a more precise comparison to understand the role of the synergistic effect of metal and support on catalytic selectivity. Metal Ru does not affect the types of adsorption intermediates, as it plays a role as a site for H₂ dissociation, while utilizing the H-spillover effect to participate in the reaction. The selective generation of intermediates mainly depends on the surface properties of MnO_x support, and formate can be generated on MnO_x–O_v, while it is absent on MnO_x–C. The formate can be further hydrogenated to methane under the condition that Ru provides the active H species. These findings bear profound implications for elucidating the CO₂ hydrogenation mechanism and advancing the development of highly selective catalysts.

Results and Discussion

Proving the Preparation of RuMn Catalysts with Different Surface Oxygen Vacancies

Two MnO samples with different surface densities of oxygen vacancies were prepared. They were indicated as MnO_x–C and MnO_x–O_v, where the first corresponds to a nearly clean surface and the second to high density of surface oxygen vacancies. They were derived from the MnO₂ with different morphology through defined synthesis methodologies^[16] (Figure S2). The sample obtained after loading of Ruthenium, RuMn–C and RuMn–O_v, respectively, presents near-spherical nanograins with similar MnO crystal structure (PDF #006-0592)^[16a] even after reduction (Figures S3 and S4). Even with the same crystalline structure in RuMn–C and RuMn–O_v, the changes in surface chemical properties deriving from the different concentrations of oxygen vacancies could be identified. Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) detects unpaired electrons in the materials, while both Mn²⁺ (¹⁷) and oxygen vacancy^[15] contributed to the EPR signal. It can be seen that stronger EPR intensity for the RuMn–O_v indeed possesses a higher density of oxygen vacancies (Figure 1a).

Furthermore, nearly *in-situ* X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to analyse the surface chemical state of the reduced catalyst (Figure S5). The electron binding energy of the Ru 3d_{5/2} spectrum in the RuMn–O_v catalyst was 0.4 eV higher than that of the RuMn–C catalyst (Figure S5a), implying its relative electron deficiency (Ru^{δ+}). This was mainly due to the strong interaction between the Ru and oxygen vacancies. Generally, the magnitude of peak splitting of Mn 3s spectra was diagnostic of Mn oxidation state^[18]. The Mn 3s spectra of RuMn–C and RuMn–O_v were the same with 6.0 eV multiplet splitting of Mn²⁺ (MnO) (Figure S5b). However, upon normalising the Mn 2p spectra of both catalysts and subsequently generating different spectra, an additional peak at approximately 640.1 eV was detectable in RuMn–O_v, in contrast to RuMn–C catalyst (Figure 1b). This distinctive feature is likely attributable to the emergence of Mn^{2-x} species, formed due to the oxygen vacancy formation. Meanwhile, the RuMn–O_v catalyst possessed lower surface O/Mn (lower than 1) compared with RuMn–C catalyst (Figure S6 and Supplementary Note 1). These findings provided conclusive evidence that the RuMn–O_v catalyst possessed a notably higher density of surface oxygen vacancies.

Figure 1. Comparison of surface oxygen affinity for RuMn-O_v and RuMn-C catalysts. a: Nearly *in-situ* EPR spectra of the reduced RuMn-O_v and RuMn-C. b: Normalising the Mn 2p spectra (nearly *in-situ* XPS) of RuMn-C and RuMn-O_v catalysts and subsequently generating different spectra. c: Temperature programmed profiles, and d: integrated area H₂-O₂ titration experiments.

The oxygen adsorption capacity could be used to evaluate the surface oxygen vacancy density of MnO^[17, 19]. RuMn-C and RuMn-O_v catalysts possessed similar reducibility based on the H₂ temperature programmed reduction (H₂-TPR) results with an almost overlapping reduction peak at 193°C (Figure S7). The three times cyclic H₂-O₂ titration experiment, involving oxygen pre-adsorption at 50°C followed by programmed temperature ramping in H₂, was used to quantitatively assess the O₂ adsorption capacity derived from the oxygen affinity over the vacancy. The maximum in H₂ consumption of RuMn-O_v was 187°C during the three cyclic experiments, e.g. higher than that of RuMn-C (around 125°C) (Figure 1c). Meanwhile, the adsorption capacity of the RuMn-O_v catalyst was 10-15 times that of RuMn-C catalyst by integrating the H₂ consumption peaks (Figure 1d).

Additionally, the catalysts' oxygen affinity was demonstrated by their characteristic color changes upon exposure to air after reduction (Figure S8). After the reduction process, the colour of the catalysts changes from black (MnO₂) to green (MnO). Then, the RuMn-O_v changed to brown within 2 minutes in air, whereas most RuMn-C remained green even after being exposed to air for 1 hour.

Additionally, the average particle size of Ru on RuMn-O_v was only 1.0 nm, while that on RuMn-C was 2.2 nm, according to the statistical analysis of the transmission electron microscope results (Figure 2). Both catalysts mainly exposed [220] and [111] crystal planes. Therefore, the two catalysts displayed congruent crystal structures and exposed identical crystal facets, indicating that the higher dispersion of Ru on RuMn-O_v originated from the surface atomic defect sites, such as the oxygen vacancies^[20]. The strong interaction was consistent with the higher valence of Ru species for RuMn-O_v (Figure S5a).

Figure 2. Electron microscope analysis. HAADF-STEM images and Ru nanoparticle size distribution of (a-c) reduced RuMn-O_v and (d-f) reduced RuMn-C.

In conclusion, the above experiments evidence that two RuMn catalysts with a similar crystal structure but different surface oxygen vacancy densities were successfully synthesised.

CO₂ Reduction Activities

The CO₂ reduction performances as a function of reaction temperature at the steady-state regime are shown in Figure 3a. The RuMn-C catalyst maintained nearly 100% CO selectivity in the reaction temperature range of 320-500°C, while the RuMn-O_v catalyst showed lower CO selectivity, less than 10% below 400°C. The increased CO selectivity above 400°C for the RuMn-O_v catalyst is mainly due to the thermodynamic factor that high reaction temperature favours the reverse water gas shift (RWGS) reaction^[21]. By increasing the WHSV (weight hourly space velocity) to 240 000 ml·g⁻¹·h⁻¹ and maintaining CO₂ conversion below 10% for both catalysts, RuMn-C still maintained 100% CO selectivity, while RuMn-O_v showed high CH₄ selectivity (Figure S9). The RuMn-O_v had better CO₂ hydrogenation activity, even if its activation energy (84.6 kJ·mol⁻¹ for CH₄) was higher than that of RuMn-C (71.9 kJ·mol⁻¹ for CO) (Figure S10). Thus, the improved activity is due to the higher pre-exponential factor, e.g., a higher number of active sites rather than a lower energy surface path^[22]. Surprisingly, ultra-high CO selectivity was obtained on RuMn-C catalyst when the Ru loading increased from 0.5% to 5.0% wt. (CO selectivity > 93%, Figures 3b and S11-S13), notwithstanding the higher Ru loading should promote methanation (thus a decrease in CO selectivity), being known as an excellent methanation catalyst due to the strong C-O bond dissociation ability^[23]. This is the first evidence that dominant CO formation was archived over such a high-loading-content Ru-based catalyst (Table S2)^[5, 23a, 24]. Therefore, the selective behaviour in these catalysts is not directly related to Ru nanoparticles.

Besides, Ni active metal with 2% loading on MnO_x-O_v support were also tested, which exhibits almost 100% CO selectivity (Figure 3b), although the Ni nanoparticles were also considered as the active phase for the methanation reaction^[25].

Figure 3. Catalytic performance and temperature programmed experiments. a: Temperature programmed CO₂ reduction activities of RuMn-O_v and RuMn-C catalysts. b: CO₂ reduction performances of MMn-C and MMn-O_v (M=Ru or Ni) catalysts at 400 °C. c: The H₂: CO₂ ratio effect on CO selectivity at 400°C. d: CO hydrogenation activity with varied H₂:CO ratio. Reaction condition:100 mg catalyst, CO (5 ml·min⁻¹), H₂ (15-90 ml·min⁻¹), N₂ as equilibrium gas ensured a total flow of 100 ml·min⁻¹. e: CO₂+H₂-TPR and CO+H₂-TPR over RuMn-O_v catalyst, the inset was the local magnification for the yellow region.

Increasing H₂ partial pressure is beneficial to hydrogenate further the reaction intermediates to form CH₄, resulting in lower CO selectivity^[26]. However, the CO selectivity of the RuMn-C catalyst was not significantly affected by the H₂:CO₂. Even if H₂:CO₂ was increased to 6:1, the CO selectivity remained at 94.6% (Figure 3c). Whereas the CO selectivity of the RuMn-O_v catalyst decreased as the H₂:CO₂ ratio increased.

In addition, long-term high-temperature reactions might also result in a decrease in CO selectivity due to the particle sintering^[27]. The two catalysts maintain significant selectivity differences after the reaction at 400°C for 48 h, although the CO₂ conversion slightly decreased, especially at the initial stage within 10 h (Figure S14). Moreover, the CO hydrogenation performance was often used to evaluate the selectivity of CO₂ hydrogenation, which was related to the metal properties^[22a, 27-28]. Higher H₂ partial pressure will positively shift CO methanation reaction equilibrium and allow a higher reaction rate. However, even if the H₂:CO ratio increased to 18, there was no obvious CH₄ generation for both the RuMn-C and RuMn-O_v catalysts (Figure 3d).

CO₂+H₂ and CO+H₂ temperature programmed reaction results of RuMn-O_v were compared in Figure 3e. The light-off temperature of CO methanation was about 68°C higher than that of CO₂ methanation, and the former reaction rate was far lower than that of the later by comparing the slope. It showed that the energy barrier of CO methanation was much higher than that of CO₂ methanation, indicating that CO was not the key intermediate in the methanation process of RuMn-O_v catalyst^[27]. Therefore, the effect of support surface properties on selectivity had to be considered rather than focusing only on the metal itself and the hydrogenation activity of CO.

The Role of Ru Nanoparticles on the Selectivity

It is widely accepted that Ru nanoparticles with a smaller size have a weaker CO adsorption ability, determining a faster carbon monoxide desorption and higher CO selectivity. Although the Ru nanoparticle size in RuMn-C and RuMn-O_v catalysts is comparable, the former shows an average size of 2.2 nm with respect to only 1.0 nm of RuMn-O_v (Figure 2). Thus, RuMn-C, with a larger average Ru particle size, exhibited an exceptional selectivity of nearly 100% towards CO in CO₂ hydrogenation.

Increasing the Ru loading content to 5 wt.%, the average particle size of Ru on 5%RuMn-O_v increased to 2.1 nm, and that on 5%RuMn-C reached 3.7 nm (Figure S15). The Ru particle size did not directly influence the reaction selectivity (Figure 3b). In addition, modifying the electronic state of a metal to form an electron-deficient center (M^{δ+}) could inhibit π back-donation and weaken the adsorption of CO^[4], resulting in higher CO selectivity^[22a, 29]. However, the RuMn-O_v catalyst with lower Ru electron density (Ru^{δ+}) presented higher CH₄ selectivity, indicating that the electronic state of Ru was also not the key factor affecting CO₂ selectivity.

In recent years, it has also been reported that strong metal-support interaction (SMSI) between VIII-group metals and reducible supports benefited the hydrogenation of CO₂ to CO^[7, 30]. Due to the SMSI effect, the reducible support migrated to the metal surface to form an encapsulation structure of the metal nanoparticle, inhibiting the adsorption of small molecules such as CO and H₂^[31]. However, there was no detectable Mn species on the surface of Ru nanoparticles on RuMn-C by energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) linear scanning (Figure S16), implying that the high CO selectivity of the RuMn-C catalyst was independent of the SMSI effect.

These experiments indicate that the local structure of Ru species was not the determining factor in influencing the selectivity of CO₂ hydrogenation. Therefore, the mechanism of CO₂ hydrogenation does not occur over the Ru nanoparticles or at the interface. Nevertheless, without Ru nanoparticles, the activity is much lower, discussion later. They generate spillover hydrogen, migrating over the oxide to hydrogenate the intermediate species formed on it.^[22b]

Dependence of Selectivity on Oxygen Vacancy on the MnO Surface

In-situ diffuse reflection Fourier infrared spectroscopy (DRIFTS) experiments were used to understand these aspects. The results for RuMn-C in a feed of CO₂+H₂ at increasing reaction temperature from 50° to 350 °C are shown in Figure S17 and Figure 4a. No gaseous CH₄ was observed during the whole DRIFT test on RuMn-C catalyst (Figure S17), which was consistent with the activity test results. The strength of bridge adsorption CO (CO_{br}) decreased with the temperature, while the linear adsorption CO (CO_{lin}) and weak gaseous CO appeared at 150°C. The IR vibrational spectra of CO₂ adsorption species were mainly in the range of 1,000-1,800 cm⁻¹ (Figure 4a). Two adsorption intermediates were present on RuMn-C catalyst at 50°C, which can be attributed to carboxylate [(i), 1667 and 1199 cm⁻¹] and bidentate carbonate [(ii), 1541, 1308, and 1047 cm⁻¹] respectively^[32]. The intensity of carboxylate species showed a downward trend, especially at 150°C, and the signal disappeared almost completely at 350°C.

In contrast, the bidentate carbonate signal intensity slightly increases during temperature ramping. The carboxylate consumption and CO formation strongly correlate, indicating that carboxylate was the key intermediate for RWGS reaction over the RuMn-C catalyst.

The transient DRIFT was further employed to analyse the reactivity of surface intermediates (Figure 4b and Figure S18). The RuMn-C catalyst was pretreated by reduction (H₂) and purging (Ar), and then CO₂ was introduced into the catalyst at 350°C for 30 min. The bidentate carbonate was the only intermediate, and its signal intensity slightly decreased during the H₂ purge. It could be concluded that the bidentate carbonate was an inactive species. Therefore, the reaction mechanism of hydrogenation of CO₂ to CO over the RuMn-C catalyst can be summarised as follows: (i) CO₂ was first adsorbed on the hydroxyl groups on the surface of the RuMn-C catalyst to form carboxylate^[33] and (ii) then the carboxylate was further decomposed into product CO with the bidentate carbonate as a spectator.

The RuMn-O_v catalyst showed more complex surface intermediates, and the formate species [(iii), 1593, 1403, and 1375 cm⁻¹] was present besides carboxylate and bidentate carbonate (Figures 4c and S19). The 1593 cm⁻¹ signal corresponds to the asymmetric vibration of formate, while the 1403 cm⁻¹ and 1375 cm⁻¹ signals correspond to the symmetric vibration^[34]. The enhanced CO₂ adsorption over RuMn-O_v was an important reason for formate formation^[12]. During the temperature ramping, the carboxylate species were gradually consumed with a parallel formation of CO, similarly to the RuMn-C catalyst. In contrast, the bidentate carbonate (a spectator for RuMn-C catalyst) decreased with increasing temperature, while the formate species increased in intensity and accumulated on the catalyst surface. The formate species were derived from the hydrogenation of carbon-contained surface-adsorbed species^[35].

The three intermediates coexisted after CO₂ pre-adsorption (Figures 4d and S20). However, they were all rapidly consumed in H₂ purging within 4 min from the start, forming CH₄. Therefore, adsorbed species on the surface of RuMn-O_v had more reactivity than over RuMn-C. Assuming a first-order dependence from the concentration of the adsorbed species, their rate of disappearance thus increases linearly with their surface concentration. However, DRIFTS data indicate a higher rate, also normalising to the concentration of adspecies. Thus, the intrinsic rate enhancement is related to the higher concentration of oxygen vacancies.

Ye et al.^[36] found that the oxygen affinity of the catalyst was beneficial to the enhancement of CO₂ adsorption by DFT calculation. RuMn-C catalyst had two adsorption peaks at 97 and 171 °C in CO₂ temperature programmed desorption (CO₂-TPD) shown in Figure S21; the former was assigned to physical adsorption, and the latter was chemical adsorption. RuMn-O_v had a strongly enhanced CO₂ desorption peak at about 177°C. The oxygen affinity (linked to surface oxygen vacancies) contributing to the stronger CO₂ adsorption ability of RuMn-O_v might also change the intrinsic reactivity of the adspecies leading to the formation of CH₄.

In addition, large amounts of adsorbed CO species are present on the RuMn-O_v catalyst (Figure S20), which might come from the decomposition of carboxylate and formate^[37]. The adsorption peak of linearly coordinated CO (CO_{lin}) quickly decreased when

purging with H₂. It had been proved that CO was not the key intermediate for the methanation of the RuMn-O_v catalyst. Therefore, the decrease in the adsorption peak of CO_{lin} was mainly caused by desorption.

DRIFT results of CO₂ pre-adsorption followed by Ar purging were shown in Figure S22. The CO_{lin} adsorption peak also showed a similar decline trend. This revealed the small amount of CO produced during CO₂ hydrogenation activity testing (Figure 3b). In addition, the surface intermediates on RuMn-O_v were more reactive than those on RuMn-C, because they are all further hydrogenated to formate and eventually completely converted.

Figure 4. Temperature programmed CO₂+H₂-DRIFTs ramping from 50 to 350 °C over a: RuMn-C and c: RuMn-O_v. H₂-DRIFTs after CO₂ pre-adsorption for 30 min at 350 °C over b: RuMn-C and d: RuMn-O_v. (i) Carboxylate, (ii) Bidentate carbonate, and (iii) Formate. e: The surface formate (HCOO*, 1386 cm⁻¹), bridging CO adsorption (CO_{br1}-1, 1886 and CO_{br1}-2, 1934 cm⁻¹), linear CO (CO_{lin}, 2005-1959 cm⁻¹), and methane (3016 cm⁻¹) species versus time during the H₂ purging for CO₂-preadsorbed RuMn-O_v catalyst. f: Comparison of CO₂ adsorption intermediate between RuMn-O_v and MnO_x-O_v at 30 °C. g: HCOOH pre-adsorption followed by H₂ temperature programmed surface reaction (HCOOH-TPSR).

Based on the above DRIFTs results, it may be indicated that forming formate on the surface of the RuMn-O_v catalyst was a critical factor contributing to its high selectivity towards CH₄. The hypothesis could be further verified by quantitatively analysing the variation of the surface species on the RuMn-O_v catalyst based on the data from Figure 4d and Figure S20. The normalised absorbance of surface formate (HCOO*, 1386 cm⁻¹), bridging CO adsorption (CO_{br1}-1, 1886 and CO_{br1}-2, 1934 cm⁻¹), linear CO (CO_{lin}, 2005-1959 cm⁻¹), and methane (3016 cm⁻¹) species versus time during H₂ purging after CO₂ adsorption was shown in Figure 4e. A noteworthy finding was the significant negative correlation between methane production and formate consumption, while CO species exhibited an initial increase followed by a subsequent decrease. The bridging-adsorption CO with higher reactivity was predominantly retained within 5 min, whereas the weak adsorption of linear CO was removed by purging. This trend indicates that the formate acts as the main intermediate in the formation of CH₄ over the RuMn-O_v catalyst rather than CO intermediate. Notably, the formate formation could also occur on the MnO_x-O_v support without Ru-loaded^[38] (Figures 4f and S23), indicating that formate formation was independent of metal or metal-support interface.

However, the MnO_x-O_v supports possessed nearly 100% CO selectivity (Figure S24). This was consistent with the literature reported that surface formate species on oxide that were far away from the active metal can directly dehydrogenate to form CO^[22a, 39]. As shown in Figure 4f, the RuMn-O_v catalyst presented a significantly enhanced O-C-O asymmetric bending compared with MnO_x-O_v. It could be related to interface species between Ru nanoparticles and MnO_x-O_v support. However, a correlation was not observed between the size of the Ru nanoparticles (thus interfacial perimeter) and the intensity of this band. The attribution is that it is a surface CO₂ chemisorbed species interacting with spillover hydrogen, thus the intermediate to formate and its further hydrogenation to CH₄.

Furthermore, the CH₄ was observed over RuMn-C during HCOOH pre-adsorption followed by H₂ temperature programmed surface reaction (HCOOH-TPSR) (Figure 4g). These DRIFTs and HCOOH-TPSR results thus show that formate generation depends on the support's high oxygen vacancy and spillover H (generated at Ru nanoparticles), which induce the further hydrogenation of formates to methane.

Density functional theory (DFT) computational quantum mechanical modelling was used to verify the relationship between formate generation and catalytic surface oxygen defect (Figure S25-S29 and Figure 5a-5b). The formate adsorption strength over MnO-O_v (-364.2 kJ·mol⁻¹) was higher than that over MnO-C (-216.2 kJ·mol⁻¹), which would promote the formation of the formate intermediate. Furthermore, the possible formation pathway of formate was analysed as shown in Figure 5a-5b. The formate species (HCOO* or HCOOH*) derived from adsorbed COOH have a lower energy barrier than the direct hydrogenation of CO₂. The HCOOH formation energy barrier (E_f) was only 41.5 kJ·mol⁻¹ over MnO-O_v, while it was up to 192.9 kJ·mol⁻¹ over MnO-C. Therefore, the surface oxygen defects induce a higher formate generation and a change in their intrinsic reactivity, in agreement with the experimental results.

Metal Ru and MnO synergy through H-spillover

The enhanced H spillover facilitates the hydrogenation of CO₂^[40], as commented above. The surface oxygen vacancies promote the creation of surface hydroxyl groups^[41]. The H-D isotope exchange DRIFTS experiments are shown in Figure S30. The stronger O-D and O-H vibration peaks observed over RuMn-O_v indicate a superior H spillover ability in comparison to RuMn-C. Additionally, the similarly weak H-D exchange DRIFT intensities recorded for both RuMn-C and 5%RuMn-C suggested that the surface oxygen vacancy density has a greater influence on H spillover than the amount of Ru metal^[42]. Consequently, the stronger H spillover also contributed to the higher methanation activity and selectivity^[40]. As mentioned above, the CH₄ selectivity of RuMn-O_v catalyst increased with the increased H₂:CO₂ and Ru loading content, while they were insensitive for the selectivity of RuMn-C. These all demonstrate the importance of formate formation and efficient dissociation of H₂ for CH₄ generation. In our prior research concerning MnO-based catalysts, we have illustrated that the augmentation of H-spillover, in absence of formate formation, does not foster methane production^[22b].

In summary, MnO_x-O_v support has significantly more surface oxygen vacancies than MnO_x-C support, resulting in an enhanced CO₂ adsorption ability and a higher intrinsic reactivity of formate intermediates during CO₂ hydrogenation (Figure 5c). The role of Ru nanoparticles is to generate spillover H, while does not participate directly in the mechanism of reaction. The surface oxygen species favour a faster spillover hydrogen diffusion, thus determining the selectivity to methane from this perspective. Therefore, the selectivity of CO₂ hydrogenation is governed by the interplay between support-dependent formate formation and metal-dependent H₂ dissociation.

Figure 5. The formation energy barrier for forming COOH and HCOO (or HCOOH) species over a, MnO-C and b, MnO-O_v. c, The scheme of the catalytic pathway for the CO₂ hydrogenation over RuMn-C and RuMn-O_v.

Conclusion

Two RuMn catalysts, RuMn-O_v and RuMn-C, were effectively synthesised with the sole differences being the surface oxygen vacancy content. The RuMn-O_v catalyst demonstrates a pronounced CH₄ selectivity within the temperature range of 300-500°C, whereas RuMn-C exhibits nearly 100% CO selectivity. The variation in selectivity does not attributable to differences in metal properties (such as electronic state, particle size, and the strong metal-support interaction effect) or the metal's CO hydrogenation ability. In situ DRIFTS studies have revealed that formate intermediates are generated on the surface of high-defective RuMn-O_v catalyst, which is absent on the low-defective RuMn-C catalyst. Furthermore, the formate intermediates efficiently hydrogenate into methane with spillover H from metal Ru. Previous studies have overly emphasized the impact of metal or metal/support interface properties on

catalytic selectivity, often neglecting the significance of the support itself in the selective generation of intermediates. These findings provide a comprehensive understanding of the mechanism underlying CO₂ hydrogenation reaction and serve as a crucial foundation for the design of highly selective catalysts.

Supporting Information

Methods, catalyst morphology and crystal structure, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy results, temperature programmed experiment, supplementary CO₂ performance, DRFITS results, DFT model.

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Keywords: CO₂ reduction • Catalytic selectivity • Formate intermediate • Surface oxygen vacancies

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